

Synthesis and Physiological Activity of some *N*-Alkyl-substituted-pyrazino-1,4-benzoxazines

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4*N*-Alkyl-substituted-7,8-diphenyl-2*H*-pyrazino[2,3-*g*]-1,4-benzoxazin-3-ones (7), 6-acetamido-7-nitro-(4), 6-amino-7-nitro-(5), 6,7-diamino-4*N*-alkyl substituted-2*H*-1,4-benzoxazin-3-one (6) have been synthesised and their antibacterial activities have been evaluated.

4 *N*-Alkyl-substituted-2*H*-1,4-benzoxazin-3-ones have been reported to possess diverse physiological properties¹. In an effort to prepare 4*N*-alkyl-substituted-6,7-diamino-2*H*-1,4-benzoxazin-3-ones as a potential source for the synthesis of a variety of heterocyclic compounds, we have synthesised the title compounds starting from the easily accessible 2,4-dinitrophenol.

Partial reduction of 2,4-dinitrophenol gave 2-amino-4-nitrophenol which on being refluxed with ethyl bromoacetate in acetone and dry potassium carbonate mixture resulted 6-nitro-2*H*-1,4-benzoxazine (1; mp, m.m.p.² 240°). It was alkylated (1a) and further reduced³ to give the 6-amino compound (2) which on acetylation (3) followed by nitration with aluminium nitrate⁴, resulted 6-acetamido-7-nitro-4*N*-alkyl-substituted compound (7). It was hydrolysed to 5 followed by reduction using palladium-charcoal⁷ to give 4*N*-alkyl-substituted-6,7-diamino-2*H*-1,4-benzoxazin-3-one (6). Compound 6 on condensation with various 1,2-diketones formed the corresponding pyrazinobenzoxazin-3-ones (7) which were characterised by spectral data. All the compounds were screened and observed for the biological activity⁸.

Experimental

Ir spectra (KBr) was recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra on a Varian A-90 (EM-390) instrument using TMS as an

internal reference and mass spectra on a Varian MAT CH7 spectrometer at 70 eV using direct inlet system. Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected.

6-Acetamido-8-nitro-2*H*-1,4-benzoxazin-3-(4-methyl) one (4): Aluminium nitrate (0.05 mol) was dissolved in acetic acid (20 ml) at 25° and acetamido compound (0.05 mol) was added to it while stirring, then kept for 4 h and diluted. The resulting solid was recrystallised from methanol (84%), m.p. 304°, C₁₁H₁₁N₃O₅; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 335 (NH-CO-CH₃), 1 680 (N-CO) and 1 650 cm⁻¹ (NH-COCH₃); δ (CDCl₃) 2.18 (3H, s, NH-CO-CH₃), 3.38 (3H, s, N-CH₃), 4.74 (2H, s, CH₂-CO), 7.47 (1H, s, C₈-ArH), 7.62 (1H, s, C₈-ArH) and 10.89 (1H, b, NHC(=O)CH₃).

6-Amino-7-nitro-2*H*-1,4-benzoxazin-3-(4-methyl) one (5): Compound 4 (0.05 mol) was hydrolysed with 5% ethanolic potassium hydroxide (200 ml) under reflux for 1 h, then poured in crushed ice. The resulting solid was recrystallised from methanol (56%), m.p. 277°d, C₉H₉N₃O₄; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 460—3 340 (NH₂) and 1 650 cm⁻¹ (NH-COCH₂); δ (DMSO-d₆) 3.39 (3H, s, N-CH₃), 4.6 (2H, s, CH₂CO), 6.61 (1H, s, C₈-ArH) and 7.40 (2H, b, NH₂).

6,7-Diamino-4*N*-methyl-2*H*-1,4-benzoxazin-3-one (6): To 5 (0.05 mol) dissolved in methanol, activated palladium-charcoal (10% of Pd, 2 g) was added and hydrogen gas was passed (30 lb in⁻²) for 4 h. The charcoal was then filtered out and the contents diluted with water. The resulting solid on recrystallisation from acetic acid gave colourless fluffy substance (32%), m.p. 222°, C₉H₁₁N₃O₃; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 400—3 200 (NH₂) and 1 650 (N-COCH₂); δ (DMSO-d₆) 3.89—4.26 (6H, b, CH₂, NH₂ and NH₂ merged broad peak), 6.31 (1H, s, C₈-ArH) and 6.32 (1H, s, C₈-ArH).

7,8-Diphenyl-2*H*-pyrazino[2,3-*g*]-1,4-benzoxazin-3-(4-alkyl)one (7): To the diamine (0.01 mol) dissolved in ethanol (25 ml), was added benzil (0.012 mol) and the mixture refluxed for 2 h. The solution was then poured into crushed ice and filtered.

Crystallisation from methanol-chloroform mixture gave a solid which was adsorbed on neutral alumina and eluted with benzene-chloroform mixture (3 : 1) to give colourless crystals: 7c ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 00—2 900b (CH₂) and 1 700 cm⁻¹ (N(CH₃) CO-CH₃); δ (DMSO-d₆) 4.92 (2H, s, CH₃), 3.38 (3H, s, N-CH₃), 7.41 (10H, s, ArH), 7.61 (1H, s, C₁₀-ArH) and 7.79 (1H, s, C₈-ArH); m/z 367; 7k ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 040—2 910b (CH₂) and 1 685 cm⁻¹ (N(CH₃)COCH₃); δ (DMSO-d₆) 4.9 (2H, s, CH₃), 3.38 (3H, t, NCH₂CH₃), 4.17 (2H, q, CH₂CH₃), 7.4—7.6 (10H, m, ArH), 7.61 (1H, s,

C₁₀-ArH) and 7.8 (1H, s, C₈-ArH); 7s ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 020—2 900b (CH₂) and 1 690b cm⁻¹ (N-C=O); δ (DMSO-d₆) 4.9 (2H, s, CH₂), 4.06 (2H, d, NCH₂), 5.85 (1H, m, NCH₂-CH=CH₂), 5.00—5.12 (2H, d, NCH₂-CH=CH₂), 7.34—7.5 (10H, m, ArH), 7.58 (1H, s, C₁₀-ArH) and 7.75 (1H, s, C₈-ArH); m/z 393.

Biological testing: All the title compounds (7) were screened *in vitro* against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* using cup-plate agar diffusion method⁵ and the results were compared with penicillin (100% inhibition). The compounds exhibited 0—81 and 12—91% inhibition at concentrations 25 and 50 mg ml⁻¹ respectively against *S. aureus* and 10—56 and 14—82% inhibition at concentrations 25 and 50 mg ml⁻¹ respectively against *E. coli*.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF 7,8-SUBSTITUTED(R')-2H-PYRAZINO[2,3-g]-1,4-BENZOXAZIN-3(4R)-ONE (7)*

Compd. no.	R'	Yield %	M.p.** °C
R=Methyl			
7a	H	61	315
b	Methyl	45	328
c	Phenyl	52	256
d	4-Chlorophenyl	65	287
e	4-Methoxyphenyl	36	281
f	4-Methylphenyl	60	262
g	4-Nitrophenyl	74	274
h	Furyl	9	248
R=Ethyl			
i	H	20	220
j	Methyl	35	162
k	Phenyl	60	172
l	4-Chlorophenyl	42	284
m	4-Methoxyphenyl	12	174
n	4-Methylphenyl	16	234
o	4-Nitrophenyl	68	192
p	Furyl	17	261
R=Allyl			
q	H	19	115
r	Methyl	25	128
s	Phenyl	23	194
t	4-Chlorophenyl	41	135
u	4-Methoxyphenyl	85	230
v	4-Methylphenyl	57	148
w	4-Nitrophenyl	48	168
x	Furyl	34	141

* Satisfactory C and H analysis obtained for all the compounds.

** Recrystallisation of pyrazines from methanol and chloroform.

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